

The Free trade Microeconomics: The theory of the price

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December 15, 2023

Abstract

The model incorporates the correlation between prices and consumption; a mixture of intuitive considerations, we study the econometrical side carefully and we shed our attention on consumption economical behavior, consumption might be negative in which case we use our model to calculate the level of debt that allows some people to disadvantage others in a half time; we define g as the inflationary debt and study carefully its behavior empirically aside another fruitful study of the surplus any economy under our simplistic model delivers under absence of arbitrage and a low-rate environment. As the correlation between S&P 500 Stock share and GDP is shown previously to be weak we use such a metaphor to study the behavior of our little ideal economy with deep care. Another important result is the fact the volatility of the real price of some companies indexed in S&P is unpredictable under our deep-learned model, we always see difference while not expecting the quick curtosis of our model.

JEL Classification. B27, C01 .

Key words and phrases. Free trade, economics, fractional volatility, surplus

1 Introduction

Consumption is a medieval issue, this article is incorporating a political topic using statistical simple equations and econometrics, we suppose our economy belongs to a country which has trade outward, the incoming of politics lies in a question, it's when our short precarious topic diverges from the essence of economics into politics, the question lies in proposing a model for consumption mixed with prices in the economy,

however we were content of suggesting an euphoric equation to model such a precarious notion where there is dread, the importance of this article is a deep-learned model that falls into economical results under the S&P 500 shelter where the weakness of correlation between the Stock market and real GDP was seen as an assumption that specifies our results regarding how Surplus in the economy varies with respect to interest rate, with a weak correlation the interest rate seems to be high where there is more surplus and the effect of an augmentation in short rates has a sharp echo than in the cases this correlation is strong or medium, we assigned respectively the values of $\gamma = 0.1; 0.5; 1$ to the levels of correlation between the Stock market and the real economy; the surplus we talked about is a result of Futures pricing under a low interest rate and no arbitrage opportunities. Afterward we define the debt level that accounts for both inflation and consumption, we define g as the inflationary debt, the behavior of such a deterministic value is deemed to follow a geometric relation.

Christopher Ball and Jack Frenc (2021) have studied the correlation between S&P Stock and real GDP, their finding was a weak correlation on which we had layed off the result regarding interest rate effects on prices or arguably the behavior of companies with respect to the bank when the economy can't breath and we got a surplus. Jolanta D. and Algirdas M. (2011) have discussed the free trade liberalisation in a free economy, they come up with a deep study for liberelisation impacts, the question of free trade has political roots as we might upraise in the following. We have supposed S&P 500 volatility is fractional and indeed has a long memory, Peng Wu, Jean-François Muzy and Emmanuel Bacry (2022) have studied some indexes closely and had shown that S&P 500 memory is long.

2 Model

Our model has shown a relation between consumption and real prices, we are accounting for a deep study that takes inflation into account, every time there is an operation locally or with a foreign nation prices are learnt to augment due to this while the future consumption is nothing else than the current consumption plus the price.

$$\begin{aligned} p_{t+1} &= (\alpha + \beta)p_t + h_t \epsilon_t \\ C_{t+1} &= (\mathbb{1}_{E[p_{t+1}/\beta=0] \geq p_t} + \mathbb{1}_{E[p_{t+1}/\alpha=0] \geq p_t})C_t + p_t \end{aligned}$$

Where $\alpha > 1$ and $\beta > 1$ are two random variables ruled by the severity of a stochastic function depending chiefly on both $\{\alpha = 0\}$ and $\{\beta = 0\}$, we would specify their density later on. C is consumption.

Hypothesis: α is linked to exportation and β is a local operation, any time $\alpha \neq 0$, β is null and vice versa.

We choose as a numeraire the loanable funds market in which case we could write

$$E[p_T - C_T / \mathcal{F}_t] = \exp(r(T - t))(p_t - C_t)$$

The Figarch model is specified as mean reverting equation using the following formula as a starting point:

$$\Phi(L)(1-L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Psi(L)g(z_{t-1})$$

Where ω is the mean variance and $\Phi(L)$ and $\Psi(L)$ are polynomials in the lag operator, $\Phi(L) = (1 - \Phi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Phi_p L)$ and $\Psi(L) = (1 - \Psi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Psi_p L)$ and $(1 - L)^d$ is the fractional difference operator defined by its binomial expansion:

$$(1 - L)^d = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(i-d)}{\Gamma(-d)\Gamma(i+1)} L^i$$

The function g above is allowed to include the effect past returns has on the current volatility and has the following form:

$$g(z_t) = \theta z_t + \gamma(|z_t| - E|z_t|)$$

where $z_t = \frac{\varepsilon_t}{\sigma_t}$ is the normalized innovation

we take into consideration the character volatility always shows as a mean reverting function tending to converge to a constant value and we should define it again as the following:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega)$$

It is then convenient to write the FIGARCH(1,d,1) model as:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Phi_1 h_{t-1} + g(z_{t-1}) + \Psi_1 g(z_{t-2}) \quad (1)$$

3 Consumption externalities and the bond market relevance

We would hopefully try to find out the law deciding over the behavior of investors between trade or local investments, let's be euphoric and model both $Q(\alpha = 0)$ and $Q(\beta = 0)$ starting from this condition

$$Q(\alpha = 0) + Q(\beta = 0) = 1$$

On the other hand we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& E[p_T - C_T / \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= \beta^n p_t Q(\alpha = 0) - (C_t + \sum_{i=1}^n E[p_{T-i} / \alpha = 0]) Q(\alpha = 0) \\
&\quad + \alpha^n p_t Q(\beta = 0) - (C_t + \sum_{i=1}^n E[p_{T-i} / \beta = 0]) Q(\beta = 0)
\end{aligned}$$

this would define both the two densities as the following

$$\begin{aligned}
& Q(\alpha = 0) \\
&= \frac{\exp(r(T-t))(p_t - C_t) - \alpha^n p_t + C_t - \sum_{i=1}^n E[p_{T-i} / \beta = 0]}{(\beta^n - \alpha^n) p_t - \sum_{i=1}^n E[p_{T-i} / \alpha = 0] + E[p_{T-i} / \beta = 0]}
\end{aligned}$$

$$Q(\beta = 0) = 1 - Q(\alpha = 0)$$

Which means

$$\begin{aligned}
& Q(\alpha = 0) \\
&= \frac{\exp(r(T-t))(p_t - C_t) - \alpha^n p_t + C_t + \sum_{i=1}^n E[p_{T-i} / \beta = 0]}{(\beta^n - \alpha^n) p_t - \sum_{i=1}^n E[p_{T-i} / \alpha = 0] + E[p_{T-i} / \beta = 0]}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& Q(\beta = 0) \\
&= \frac{\beta^n p_t - \exp(r(T-t))(p_t - C_t) - C_t - \sum_{i=1}^n E[p_{T-i} / \alpha = 0] + 2E[p_{T-i} / \beta = 0]}{(\beta^n - \alpha^n) p_t - \sum_{i=1}^n E[p_{T-i} / \alpha = 0] + E[p_{T-i} / \beta = 0]}
\end{aligned}$$

The two events $\{\alpha = 0\}$ and $\{E[C_T / \mathcal{F}_t] = 0\}$ are equivalent because if there is no trade the consumption would get into end because of rarity, we would try to guess the level of consumption that allows consumption to end, it's arguably the critical point for this equilibrium. Our model has the incentive of looking and investigating on how free trade is optimal for the economy.

$$\begin{aligned}
E[C_T / \mathcal{F}_t] &= E[h(p_{T-1})C_{T-1} + (\alpha + \beta)p_{T-1} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= E\left[\prod_{i=1}^n h(p_{T-i})C_t + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (\alpha + \beta)h(p_{T-i})p_{T-(i+1)} + (\alpha + \beta)p_{T-1} / \mathcal{F}_t\right]
\end{aligned}$$

with $h(p_{T-i}) = \mathbb{1}_{E[p_{T-i} / \beta = 0] \geq p_{T-i-1}} + \mathbb{1}_{E[p_{T-i} / \alpha = 0] \geq p_{T-i-1}}$

This defines the right consumption that barely gets consumption null, it's the critical consumption the government would allow households through wages and transfers.

$$C_t = \frac{-E[\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (\alpha + \beta)h(p_{T-i})p_{T-(i+1)} + (\alpha + \beta)p_{T-1} / \mathcal{F}_t]}{\prod_{i=1}^n h(p_{T-i})}$$

A negative consumption means in that regard that the consumption of many disadvantages the consumption of others or what it is classically known as externalities; we

define in the following the level of current debt until the instant T that would allow the consumer to disadvantage another consumer right away, keep in mind that they might be from different nations as usual.

$$\begin{aligned} D_s &= -P(s, T) + (p_s - p_{s-1})g(s) \\ P(s, T) &= \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^{T-s}} \end{aligned}$$

The term $p_s - p_{s-1}$ accounts for inflation that would harm the level of debt, we would find out the behavior of the function g .

Hypothesis:

$$E[D_{s+1}/\mathcal{F}_s] = D_s(1+r)$$

Arguably it is an absence of arbitrage theory that states that the level of debt is very linked to short rates in the short term.

This defines the function g behavior in our model as the following

$$E[((\alpha + \beta) - 1)p_s g(s+1)/\mathcal{F}_s] = (1+r)(p_s - p_{s-1})g(s)$$

After trying to model the level of debt, I am going to propose a model for the stock price, there is always a relation between real economy and the stock market, here is our model

$$S_{t+1} = S_t + \gamma p_t + h_t \epsilon_t$$

Where S_t is the Stock market price at time t and γ is the scale of correlation between real prices and the Stock prices.

Let's for now prices Futures under the absence of arbitrage and follow on this logic to find out which protocol is right for free trade or arguably any trade locally or with foreigners.

$$F(t, T) = S_t + \sum_{i=2}^n E^Q[\gamma(\alpha + \beta)p_{T-i}/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

Under the absence of arbitrage futures are evaluated in this way

$$F(t, T) = (1+r)^{T-t} S_t$$

This allows us to find out an important result under our model: UNDER THE ABSENCE OF ARBITRAGE AND A NULL INTEREST RATE WE HAVE

$$\sum_{i=2}^n E^Q[\gamma(\alpha + \beta)p_{T-i}/\mathcal{F}_t] = 0$$

Which means

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= 0 \\ \sum_{i=2}^n E^Q[p_{T-i}/\mathcal{F}_t] &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Which means that that under a **low interest rate** with **absence of arbitrage** there is either no correlation between the real price and the Stock Market which might be **à priori** not convenient or otherwise ideal, the other face is the existence of a surplus once in the period $[t, T - 2]$ because the condition $\sum_{i=2}^n E^Q[p_{T-i}/\mathcal{F}_t]$ induces that there are in fact negative prices which means that some companies of exportation sell their product freely because of the surplus.

4 Data discussion and Methodology

We first of all presented our model under the assumption that S&P 500 variance follows a FIGARCH process, the long memory of volatility lies in defining a new concept called the inflationary debt, as we suppose g is deterministic (we had taken a sample) we have the following

$$g(s+1) = \frac{(1+r)(p_s - p_{s-1})g(s)}{(\alpha + \beta - 1)p_s}$$

after simplification under the sample $(p_s)_{s \geq 0}$ we fall into the following

$$g(s+1) = \frac{1+r}{2}g(s)$$

Let's suppose that for a null interest rate the function g takes the unit which means a full level of debtness in which inflation is going to take effect one hundred percent.

Inflationary debt with respect to the Bank

Conclusion: As a first remark we can observe that as the interest rate augments the level of debt is immune from inflation which goes in accordance with the classical definition of interest rate, this result gives a sense to our model and supposition that we can use the bond market to guarantee $-C_t > 0$ at the maturity, while consuming $-C_t$ companies operating in the private sector are sure about disadvantaging other companies' consumptions later on by the same magnitude. Our assumption that consumption is negative had been shown to verify $E[C_T/\mathcal{F}_t] = 0$ at the cost of others. Let's now study the behavior of $var(p_t) = \nu_t$; we have

$$\begin{aligned} p_t &= - \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} E^Q[p_{T-i}/\mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= \frac{1}{\gamma} S_t \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} (1+r)^{T-i-t} - (1+r)^{T+1-i-t} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

On the other hand

$$\nu_t = \frac{1}{\gamma^2} \left(\sum_{i=2}^{n-1} (1+r)^{T-i-t} - (1+r)^{T+1-i-t} \right)^2 h_t$$

While

$$E[\nu_T/\mathcal{F}_t] = \frac{1}{\gamma^2} \left(\sum_{i=2}^{n-1} (1+r)^{T-i-t} - (1+r)^{T+1-i-t} \right)^2 \Phi^n h_t$$

There is a difference between expected variance and variance itself, here is what our model had given when we apply it to S&P 500 index

Expected variance versus variance

Conclusion: The consumption definition in our model has drawbacks which has taken effect narrowly on the pitch, as the result is showing we can write

$$E[\nu_T/\mathcal{F}_t] = \delta \nu_t$$

which means that we can not predict the course of inflation under our model. The value of Φ was assumed to verify the linear regression (1). Let's as now study the surplus of companies with respect to interest rate, let's recall the relation (2), we study the surplus behavior under three cases, weak correlation between the Stock market and real GDP, medium correlation and strong correlation.

Surplus with respect to interest rate

Conclusion: It seems as the result is showing that the relation between interest rate and surplus is sharp in a the weak correlation case.

Data: We have simulated the serie of interest rate $(r_t)_{t \geq 0}$, the index price of S&P 500 was downloaded from Investing.com.

General conclusion: Consumption sometimes is negative, which means that consuming at time t should discourage others later on, we have linked the end of future consumption to the absence of trade, afterward we seek refuge in the bond market and subscribe to a debt where the face value of the bond is $-C_t > 0$.

Under the assumption that Futures delivers a fair price we had layed out a condition which was that the price p_t is a linear function of past prices. The results we presented in the methodology section are general and allows us to consider that our model has some rational intuitive sense.

Declarations: The authors did not receive support from any organization for the submitted work. No funding was received to assist with the preparation of this manuscript. No funding was received for conducting this study. No funds, grants, or other support was received.

Ethical approval not applicable.

This article does not contain any studies with human participants performed by any of the authors.

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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